

Cardiometabolic improvements, sleep apnea reduction, and biomarker modulation under dual GLP-1RA and SGLT2i therapy: a prospective study

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Abstract

This prospective cohort study explored the cardiometabolic, sleep-related, and biomarker effects of glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RA), sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors (SGLT2i), and their combination in patients with heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF), type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), obesity, and obstructive sleep apnea (OSA). The findings revealed that therapies including GLP-1RA – either alone or in combination – consistently improved sleep apnea severity, inflammatory and glyceic biomarkers, and right ventricular–pulmonary arterial coupling. In contrast, SGLT2i monotherapy had modest effects in these domains. Notably, the addition of SGLT2i to GLP-1RA did not yield substantial additive benefits regarding sleep-related or inflammatory parameters, suggesting a dominant role of GLP-1RA. These results underscore the clinical relevance of GLP-1RA-based therapies in patients with multimorbid cardiometabolic conditions, particularly in targeting systemic inflammation and obstructive sleep apnea, both of which are critical yet often overlooked contributors to adverse outcomes in HFpEF.

Keywords

cardiometabolic syndrome, obstructive sleep apnea, GLP-1 receptor agonist

Introduction

Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) accounts for over half of all heart failure cases and is marked by heterogeneity in pathophysiology and clinical presentation. Among its most common comorbidities are type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), obesity, and obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), which together form a distinct cardiometabolic phenotype (McDonagh et al. 2023; Monda et al. 2022; Jordan et al. 2014). This phenotype is characterized by insulin resistance, inflammation, heightened sympathetic activity, endothelial dysfunction, and myocardial stiffness – mechanisms that collectively worsen HFpEF progression (Pandey et al. 2023; Altobaishat et al. 2025).

The updated 2023 ESC guidelines advocate for a patient-centered, comorbidity-based approach to HFpEF, acknowledging the absence of a unified pathophysiological model or universally effective therapy. Nevertheless, OSA remains largely underdiagnosed and insufficiently treated in HFpEF populations, despite its association with elevated pulmonary pressures, right ventricular dysfunction, and impaired exercise capacity (Javaheri et al. 2020; Borlaug et al. 2023). The interrelation between OSA, obesity, and T2DM amplifies cardiovascular risk via chronic neurohumoral and metabolic dysregulation.

Although pharmacological options are expanding, they remain limited for this multimorbid population. Sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors (SGLT2i) have shown significant benefits in HFpEF, including reduced hospitalizations and improvements in volume and inflammatory status (Lopaschuk and Verma 2020; Pandey et al. 2023). Meanwhile, glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RA) offer complementary benefits – weight reduction, endothelial protection, and cardiometabolic modulation (Li et al. 2025; Yin et al. 2025). Both drug classes extend their impact beyond glycemic control, showing promise in broader metabolic syndromes.

Recent evidence suggests that GLP-1RA may also reduce OSA severity, with meta-analyses confirming reductions in apnea–hypopnea index (AHI), even in patients without diabetes (Kow et al. 2025; Altobaishat et al. 2025). However, their use in HFpEF with coexisting OSA remains off-label and insufficiently supported by clinical data. Likewise, while SGLT2i may alleviate right-sided volume overload, evidence on their influence on sleep-disordered breathing or pulmonary hemodynamics is sparse (Borlaug et al. 2023).

Importantly, few studies have investigated the potential additive or synergistic effects of combining GLP-1RA and SGLT2i in patients who simultaneously exhibit HFpEF, T2DM, obesity, and OSA. Most cardiovascular outcome trials exclude patients with sleep disorders or omit sleep-related endpoints. Even when considered, surrogate measures such as hsCRP, AHI, or right ventricular performance are often lacking. Despite their growing importance, clinical guidelines from both the American Diabetes Association (ADA 2024) and the ESC (McDonagh et al. 2023) do not offer clear strategies for dual therapy in

patients with this complex constellation of conditions. As a result, there remains a lack of mechanistically grounded and outcome-oriented evidence to guide personalized treatment in this subgroup.

The present prospective cohort study seeks to evaluate the effects of GLP-1RA, SGLT2i, and their combination on key cardiometabolic and respiratory endpoints in patients with HFpEF, T2DM, obesity, and OSA. Specifically, the study aims to assess changes in AHI, hsCRP, natriuretic peptides, and right heart–pulmonary vascular coupling (TAPSE/sPAP), thereby addressing current therapeutic uncertainties and exploring the integrated value of dual pharmacological modulation in this high-risk phenotype.

Materials and methods

Study design and population

This was a prospective, multicenter cohort study conducted from January 2022 to June 2024 across three specialized cardiometabolic outpatient centers in Bulgaria. The objective was to evaluate the clinical, biomarker, and functional effects of treatment with glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RA), sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors (SGLT2i), or their combination in patients with a cardiometabolic profile characterized by heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF), type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), obesity, and obstructive sleep apnea (OSA).

A total of 435 patients were screened for eligibility. Of these, 162 met inclusion criteria. Sixteen declined participation, and 12 were lost to follow-up before baseline, resulting in 134 patients for final analysis. Patients were stratified into three therapeutic arms: GLP-1RA + SGLT2i (n = 54), GLP-1RA monotherapy (n = 31), and SGLT2i monotherapy (n = 49) (Fig. 1).

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria were:

- Age ≥ 18 years;
- Confirmed HFpEF (LVEF $\geq 50\%$) and NT-proBNP >125 pg/mL;
- Diagnosed with T2DM according to ADA guidelines (American Diabetes Association 2024);
- Obesity (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²);
- Obstructive sleep apnea with apnea–hypopnea index (AHI) >30 events/hour assessed by home polygraphy;
- Initiation of GLP-1RA or SGLT2i therapy within 14 days prior to enrollment;
- Written informed consent.

Exclusion criteria included:

- Recent initiation of continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) therapy (≤ 3 months);
- NYHA class IV heart failure;

- Advanced renal disease (eGFR <30 mL/min/1.73 m² or dialysis);
- Severe pulmonary disease (e.g., GOLD IV COPD, pulmonary fibrosis);
- Acute cardiovascular event (e.g., myocardial infarction, stroke) within the last 3 months;
- Participation in another ongoing clinical trial.

Sleep apnea and clinical assessments

Obstructive sleep apnea was assessed using ApneaLink™ (ResMed, San Diego, CA, USA), a validated portable type III monitoring device that measures nasal airflow, respiratory effort, pulse oximetry, and heart rate. The following parameters were analyzed: apnea–hypopnea index (AHI), oxygen desaturation index (ODI), minimum and mean SpO₂, and total recording time. The diagnostic accuracy of ApneaLink has been validated against polysomnography, demonstrating high sensitivity and specificity in detecting moderate-to-severe OSA (Ng et al. 2009).

Subjective daytime sleepiness was assessed using the Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS), a validated 8-item self-re-

port questionnaire widely used in sleep research globally. A score ≥10 was considered indicative of excessive daytime sleepiness (Johns 1991).

Cardiac function was evaluated by transthoracic echocardiography at baseline and after 6 months of follow-up. Measured parameters included left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF), E/e' ratio, indexed left atrial volume (LAVi), mitral inflow velocities, tricuspid annular plane systolic excursion (TAPSE), systolic pulmonary artery pressure (sPAP), and the right ventricular–pulmonary arterial coupling ratio (TAPSE/sPAP).

Laboratory assessments included NT-proBNP, hsCRP, HbA1c, lipid profile, and renal function markers. Clinical data, including weight, BMI, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and NYHA functional class, were recorded at each visit.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics v26.0. Data normality was tested using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Continuous variables were expressed as mean

Figure 1. Flowchart of patient selection and treatment allocation. Of the 435 patients screened, 273 were excluded (65% had no HFpEF, 35% had no OSA). A total of 134 patients were enrolled and stratified into three treatment groups: dual GLP-1RA + SGLT2i (n = 54), GLP-1RA monotherapy (n = 31), and SGLT2i monotherapy (n = 49). HFpEF – heart failure with preserved ejection fraction; OSA – obstructive sleep apnea; GLP-1RA – glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist; SGLT2i – sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor.

± standard deviation (SD) or median and interquartile range (IQR), as appropriate. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons between the three groups were performed using one-way ANOVA or the Kruskal–Wallis test for continuous variables and the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. Paired t-tests and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were used for within-group comparisons. Correlations between clinical, echocardiographic, and laboratory variables were explored using Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients. Time-to-event analyses for predefined outcomes (cardiovascular death) were performed using Kaplan–Meier survival analysis, with differences between survival curves evaluated by the log-rank test. Patients lost to follow-up were censored at the last known contact. A two-tailed p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Missing data were managed via multiple imputation. All analyses were conducted on an intention-to-treat basis.

Ethics statement

The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Sofia (Protocol No. 1316, approval date: December 13, 2021). All procedures were conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, and all participants provided written informed consent prior to enrollment.

Results

Baseline characteristics

A total of 134 patients were included in the final analysis following stratification into three treatment groups: dual therapy with GLP-1RA and SGLT2i, GLP-1RA monotherapy, and SGLT2i monotherapy. There was a predominance of male participants across all groups, with no significant difference in sex distribution. Most anthropometric measures, such as BMI and waist circumference, did not differ significantly at baseline. Measures related to breathing during sleep – such as the frequency of apneas and hypopneas, oxygen desaturation episodes, and daytime sleepiness – also did not differ significantly between the groups. Similarly, patient-reported quality of life scores and most echocardiographic parameters showed no substantial variation at baseline.

Nevertheless, some important differences were observed. Levels of NT-proBNP, a marker of cardiac strain, were significantly different among the groups at baseline. Differences were also noted in diastolic function (E/e' ratio) and left ventricular volume. Certain blood lipid values, including HDL, triglycerides, and total cholesterol, as well as resting heart rate, also showed variation. Overall, despite these few variations, most baseline characteristics were well balanced across the groups, ensuring a comparable starting point for further evaluation (Table 1).

In addition to baseline clinical and physiological profiles, the distribution of comorbidities and background pharmacotherapies was systematically recorded for all three treatment groups. The collected data included key cardiovascular conditions and commonly prescribed drug classes relevant to the management of heart failure and diabetes. An overview of these characteristics is provided in Table 2.

Changes in anthropometric, clinical, and respiratory parameters at 6 months

At the 6-month follow-up, noticeable improvements in anthropometric measures were observed. Participants receiving combination therapy showed the most pronounced reductions in body mass index, followed by those on GLP-1RA alone, while individuals treated with SGLT2i exhibited minimal change. A comparable pattern was seen for waist circumference, with the greatest reductions noted in the dual therapy group.

Respiratory outcomes also reflected significant progress over time. Reductions in both the apnea–hypopnea index and the oxygen desaturation index were most evident among patients treated with GLP-1RA-containing regimens. Furthermore, a modest but significant improvement in average nocturnal oxygen saturation was detected. In contrast, changes in the lowest oxygen saturation and time spent below 90% saturation remained similar across groups. A comprehensive overview of these findings is presented in Table 3.

Changes in echocardiographic and cardiometabolic parameters

At six months, significant improvements were observed in several cardiac markers. Ejection fraction increased notably in the dual therapy ($+3.25 \pm 0.50\%$) and GLP-1RA groups ($+3.38 \pm 0.43\%$), while the SGLT2i group showed only a minor change ($+0.35 \pm 0.45\%$; $p < 0.001$). NT-proBNP levels decreased in all groups, with the largest reduction seen in the GLP-1RA arm (-333 ± 736 pg/mL), followed by SGLT2i (-250 ± 791 pg/mL), although these differences did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.094$). A modest drop in the E/e' ratio was observed, most evident in the GLP-1RA group (-1.95 ± 1.98), compared to dual therapy (-1.25 ± 1.64) and SGLT2i (-1.13 ± 0.22 ; $p = 0.035$). Changes in LVEDV and LAVi were minimal and did not differ significantly between groups. The TAPSE/SPAP ratio improved slightly with dual therapy ($+0.08 \pm 0.09$), remained stable in GLP-1RA ($+0.04 \pm 0.05$), and showed no meaningful change in SGLT2i (-0.003 ± 0.07 ; $p < 0.001$), as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Patient-reported outcomes, as assessed by the KCCQ, demonstrated a significant overall improvement at six months, with the most notable change observed in the dual therapy group ($\Delta = 10.85 \pm 7.78$). This was significantly greater than in the GLP-1RA monotherapy group ($\Delta = 5.36 \pm 8.58$) and the SGLT2i monotherapy group ($\Delta = 2.92 \pm 5.03$; $p < 0.001$).

Table 1. Baseline clinical, echocardiographic, respiratory, and laboratory characteristics of patients stratified by treatment group.

Parameter	Dual therapy	GLP-1RA monotherapy	SGLT2i monotherapy	p-value
Sex(f/m)	14/40	13/18	16/33	0.312
Age (years)	66.48 ± 8.86	65.87 ± 9.32	58.35 ± 9.52	< 0.001*
Waist Circumference (cm)	118.60 ± 10.09	115.37 ± 10.81	116.70 ± 10.35	0.359
BMI (kg/m ²)	38.45 ± 5.34	37.09 ± 5.91	39.56 ± 6.25	0.183
KCCQ score	61.31 ± 5.98	63.81 ± 6.04	63.63 ± 5.57	0.70
Epworth Sleepiness Scale	13.58 ± 1.89	13.09 ± 2.09	13.90 ± 1.85	0.193
AHI	47.79 ± 11.86	49.11 ± 13.13	52.42 ± 11.81	0.148
Oxygen Desaturation Index	32.56 ± 7.12	30.74 ± 7.88	31.94 ± 7.17	0.545
Average SpO ₂ (%)	88.67 ± 2.60	88.16 ± 2.92	87.35 ± 2.41	0.040*
Lowest desaturation (%)	78.37 ± 6.33	77.06 ± 6.49	75.53 ± 5.86	0.071
Time <90% SpO ₂ (min)	15.83 ± 2.94	14.71 ± 3.27	13.18 ± 4.61	0.002*
LVEF (%)	61.84 ± 6.32	60.51 ± 5.56	60.26 ± 6.36	0.39
NT-proBNP (pg/mL)	906.06 ± 416.04	1071.19 ± 497.35	1230.41 ± 476.71	0.002*
E/e' ratio mean	15.13 ± 1.69	15.87 ± 2.03	16.44 ± 1.58	0.001*
LVEDV (mL)	80.97 ± 4.54	83.80 ± 3.95	83.17 ± 5.16	0.012*
LAVi (mL/m ²)	47.30 ± 6.08	50.01 ± 6.41	49.18 ± 5.05	0.085
TAPSE/sPAP	0.50 ± 0.11	0.49 ± 0.12	0.47 ± 0.10	0.334
eGFR (ml/min/1.73m ²)	69.66 ± 10.60	65.46 ± 12.67	66.23 ± 8.82	0.13
HbA1c (%)	8.72 ± 1.61	9.02 ± 1.43	8.97 ± 1.60	0.604
hsCRP (mg/L)	5.72 ± 1.18	5.47 ± 1.07	5.88 ± 1.08	0.33
Total Cholesterol (mmol/L)	5.17 ± 0.97	5.11 ± 0.89	5.55 ± 0.69	0.036*
LDL (mmol/L)	3.31 ± 1.37	3.27 ± 1.26	3.54 ± 1.24	0.574
HDL (mmol/L)	1.20 ± 0.11	1.21 ± 0.11	1.28 ± 0.11	0.001*
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	2.09 ± 0.26	2.01 ± 0.28	1.90 ± 0.22	0.001*
SBP (mmHg)	128.41 ± 18.99	131.26 ± 22.77	129.49 ± 12.06	0.778
DBP (mmHg)	79.35 ± 7.57	79.90 ± 9.40	77.37 ± 6.67	0.278
Pulse (bpm)	69.43 ± 8.79	74.00 ± 7.17	72.22 ± 7.43	0.031*

AHI – apnea–hypopnea index; BMI – body mass index; DBP – diastolic blood pressure; eGFR – estimated glomerular filtration rate; ESS – Epworth Sleepiness Scale; GLP-1RA – glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist; HbA1c – glycated hemoglobin; HDL – high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; hsCRP – high-sensitivity C-reactive protein; KCCQ – Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire; LAVi – left atrial volume index; LDL – low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; LVEF – left ventricular ejection fraction; LVEDV – left ventricular end-diastolic volume; NT-proBNP – N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide; OSA – obstructive sleep apnea; SBP – systolic blood pressure; SGLT2i – sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor; SpO₂ – peripheral oxygen saturation; TAPSE/sPAP – ratio of tricuspid annular plane systolic excursion to systolic pulmonary arterial pressure. *A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. SD – standard deviation.

Table 2. Baseline comorbidities and background pharmacotherapies of patients stratified by treatment group.

Parameter	Dual therapy (%) /n	GLP-1RA monotherapy (%) /n	SGLT2i monotherapy (%) /n	p-value
Chronic kidney disease	22.2% (n = 12)	38.7% (n = 12)	20.4% (n=10)	0.147
Atrial fibrillation	37.0% (n = 20)	35.5% (n = 11)	44.9% (n = 22)	0.662
Hypertension	87.0% (n = 47)	77.4% (n = 24)	77.6% (n = 38)	0.381
Dyslipidemia	74.1% (n = 40)	64.5% (n = 20)	71.4% (n = 35)	0.643
Coronary artery disease	20.4% (n = 11)	32.3% (n = 10)	26.5% (n = 13)	0.467
Beta blockers	92.6% (n = 50)	71.0% (n = 22)	79.6% (n = 39)	0.029
ACE/ARB	98.1% (n = 53)	41.9% (n = 13)	77.6% (n = 38)	<0.001
Mineralocorticoid receptor antagonist	35.2% (n = 19)	32.3% (n = 10)	30.6% (n = 15)	0.883
Loop diuretics	31.5% (n = 17)	25.8% (n = 8)	28.6% (n = 14)	0.853
Statins	70.4% (n = 38)	35.5% (n = 11)	57.1% (n = 28)	0.007
Metformin	61.1% (n = 33)	83.9% (n = 26)	71.4% (n = 35)	0.085
Insulins	13.0% (n = 7)	19.4% (n = 6)	6.1% (n = 3)	0.197
DPP4 inhibitors	5.6% (n = 3)	9.7% (n = 3)	2.0% (n = 1)	0.324
Sulfonylureas	11.1% (n = 6)	32.3% (n = 10)	2.0% (n = 1)	<0.001

GLP-1RA – glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist; SGLT2i – sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor; DPP4i – dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitor; ACE/ARB – angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor/angiotensin II receptor blocker. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Table 3. Changes in anthropometric and respiratory parameters at 6-month follow-up across treatment groups.

Parameter	Dual therapy	GLP-1RA monotherapy	SGLT2i monotherapy	p-value
ΔWaist Circumference (cm)	-4.81 ± 7.60	-3.35 ± 6.25	-0.16 ± 0.83	< 0.001*
ΔBMI (kg/m ²)	-2.99 ± 1.02	-2.56 ± 1.19	0.04 ± 0.20	< 0.001*
ΔESS	4.20 ± 0.86	4.10 ± 0.83	0.43 ± 0.91	< 0.001*
ΔAHI	-11.34 ± 3.17	-12.05 ± 2.99	-3.86 ± 4.80	< 0.001*
ΔODI	-5.36 ± 0.90	-2.96 ± 0.63	-0.03 ± 0.58	< 0.001*
ΔAvg. SpO ₂ (%)	1.55 ± 0.94	1.16 ± 1.07	0.83 ± 0.93	0.001*
ΔLowest SpO ₂ (%)	2.73 ± 1.29	3.02 ± 1.58	2.94 ± 1.35	0.599
ΔTime <90% SpO ₂ (min)	-3.80 ± 1.01	-4.04 ± 1.22	-3.98 ± 1.11	0.56

BMI – body mass index; ESS – Epworth Sleepiness Scale; AHI – apnea-hypopnea index; ODI – oxygen desaturation index; Avg. SpO₂ – average nocturnal oxygen saturation; Lowest SpO₂ – lowest nocturnal oxygen saturation; Time <90% SpO₂ – time spent with oxygen saturation below 90%; GLP-1RA – glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist; SGLT2i – sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. SD ± standard deviation.

Figure 2. Mean change in TAPSE/sPAP ratio at six months across treatment groups. The greatest improvement in right ventricular–pulmonary arterial coupling, as reflected by the TAPSE/sPAP ratio, was observed in the dual therapy group ($\Delta = 0.080 \pm 0.090$), followed by the GLP-1RA monotherapy group ($\Delta = 0.038 \pm 0.055$), while patients on SGLT2i monotherapy showed virtually no change ($\Delta = -0.003 \pm 0.066$). Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals. TAPSE – tricuspid annular plane systolic excursion; sPAP – systolic pulmonary arterial pressure; GLP-1RA – glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist; SGLT2i – sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor.

At six months, participants across all groups exhibited measurable improvements in several key metabolic indicators. A significant reduction in HbA1c was observed, with the greatest decrease in the dual therapy group (-1.23 ± 0.56), followed by GLP-1RA monotherapy (-1.26 ± 0.47) and SGLT2i monotherapy (-0.93 ± 0.48 ; $p = 0.004$). Renal function, as assessed by eGFR, improved most notably in the SGLT2i group ($+8.96 \pm 3.95$), while changes were more modest in the dual ($+2.67 \pm 3.23$) and GLP-1RA ($+1.76 \pm 3.76$) groups ($p < 0.001$). Inflammatory status, reflected by hsCRP levels, showed a marked reduction in both GLP-1RA-based groups (-1.19 ± 0.54 in dual therapy; -1.10 ± 0.47 in monotherapy), compared to a smaller decline in the SGLT2i group (-0.32 ± 0.48 ; $p < 0.001$).

Lipid profile improvements were also more pronounced in the dual and GLP-1RA groups, including greater reductions in total cholesterol, LDL, and triglycerides, as well as increases in HDL. Systolic and diastolic blood pressure decreased significantly in the GLP-1RA and dual therapy groups, while changes in pulse were minimal and not statistically significant (Table 4).

Survival outcomes

Survival analysis over the 6-month follow-up period revealed differences among the treatment groups. Patients receiving combination therapy exhibited the highest survival rate (92.6%), followed by those on GLP-1RA monotherapy (83.9%). The SGLT2i group had the lowest survival rate

Table 4. Metabolic and hemodynamic changes from baseline to 6-month follow-up across treatment groups.

Parameter	Dual therapy	GLP-1RA monotherapy	SGLT2i monotherapy	p-value
Δ eGFR (ml/min/1.73m ²)	2.67 ± 3.23	1.76 ± 3.76	8.96 ± 3.95	< 0.001*
Δ HbA1c (%)	-1.23 ± 0.56	-1.26 ± 0.47	-0.93 ± 0.48	0.004*
Δ hsCRP (mg/L)	-1.19 ± 0.54	-1.10 ± 0.47	-0.32 ± 0.48	< 0.001*
Δ Total Cholesterol (mmol/L)	-0.44 ± 0.06	-0.41 ± 0.05	-0.27 ± 0.10	< 0.001*
Δ LDL (mmol/L)	-0.41 ± 0.37	-0.38 ± 0.28	-0.17 ± 0.38	0.001*
Δ HDL (mmol/L)	0.06 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.05	< 0.001*
Δ Triglycerides (mmol/L)	-0.51 ± 0.13	-0.37 ± 0.10	-0.18 ± 0.08	< 0.001*
Δ SBP (mmHg)	-5.98 ± 1.16	-6.03 ± 1.30	-0.10 ± 2.07	< 0.001*
Δ DBP (mmHg)	-4.13 ± 0.52	-4.23 ± 0.62	-0.82 ± 1.59	< 0.001*

eGFR – glomerular filtration rate (mL/min/1.73 m²); HbA1c – glycated hemoglobin (%); hsCRP – high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (mg/L); total cholesterol – change in total cholesterol (mmol/L); LDL – change in low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (mmol/L); HDL – change in high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (mmol/L); triglycerides – change in triglyceride levels (mmol/L); SBP – change in systolic blood pressure (mmHg); DBP – change in diastolic blood pressure (mmHg); GLP-1RA – glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist; SGLT2i – sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant; SD ± standard deviation.

Figure 3. Kaplan–Meier survival curves for the three treatment groups over the 6-month follow-up period. GLP-1RA – glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist; SGLT2i – sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitor.

(75.5%). The mean survival times were 5.92 months for the combination group, 5.63 months for GLP-1RA, and 5.35 months for SGLT2i. The log-rank test showed a statistically significant difference between the survival distributions ($\chi^2 = 6.23$; $p = 0.044$), favoring the combination approach (Fig. 3).

Discussion

At baseline, participants in all treatment arms presented with a constellation of cardiometabolic comorbidities, with the majority being male – an observation that reflects the real-world demographic of patients suffering from HFpEF, T2DM, OSA, and obesity (Shah and Pfeffer

2012; Cohen et al. 2020). While sex was not statistically associated with treatment response, this male predominance may have implications for both the pathophysiology and responsiveness to interventions, warranting further investigation in sex-stratified analyses (Hamo et al. 2020; Kuvat et al. 2020).

One of the most notable and immediate findings in this study concerns the improvement in sleep-disordered breathing parameters. Indices such as AHI, ODI, and ESS showed clinically meaningful reductions, particularly in the dual therapy and GLP-1RA monotherapy groups. These changes likely reflect not only pharmacologic effects but also the profound impact of weight loss on upper airway mechanics, ventilatory control, and systemic in-

flammation (Dragonieri et al. 2024). The improvement in subjective daytime sleepiness (ESS) further supports the hypothesis that these therapies extend benefit beyond glycemic control and cardiovascular function. In this light, the role of GLP-1RA as a modulator of sleep apnea has recently gained significant attention, culminating in the FDA approval of GLP-1RA-based agents for the treatment of moderate-to-severe OSA in patients unable or unwilling to use CPAP (Malhotra et al. 2024; Sánchez-de-la-Torre et al. 2023). Our findings resonate with this shift in the therapeutic paradigm, particularly in high-risk, multimorbid individuals (Li et al. 2025).

These respiratory improvements paralleled a consistent and significant reduction in BMI in the GLP-1RA and combination therapy groups. The magnitude of weight loss observed – almost 3 kg/m² over 6 months in the dual therapy group – was accompanied by reductions in waist circumference and improved blood pressure profiles (Jensterle and Janež 2023). Given the strong correlation between obesity and the severity of OSA, it is plausible that weight reduction served as the central trigger for the cascade of functional and biochemical improvements reported in our cohort (Jiang et al. 2023). While our data do not directly refute this concept, they support the notion that intentional and pharmacologically induced weight loss in metabolically unhealthy individuals leads to functional gains, especially in sleep and cardiovascular performance, without detrimental effects (Blackman et al. 2016).

In contrast to the marked functional improvements, structural cardiac parameters, such as left ventricular end-diastolic volume and left atrial volume, showed no significant change over the 6-month period. However, baseline left atrial volumes were increased across groups, consistent with subclinical atrial cardiomyopathy – a well-documented yet underappreciated contributor to HFpEF, particularly in patients with long-standing hypertension, OSA, and obesity (Ilieva et al. 2025). The absence of remodeling in these structural measures may reflect the short duration of follow-up, as atrial and ventricular geometric adaptation generally occurs over longer timeframes. It is also possible that early improvements in filling pressures, natriuretic peptide dynamics, and pulmonary pressures precede anatomical reverse remodeling (Cohn et al. 2000).

The interpretation of NT-proBNP levels warrants particular nuance. Although a trend toward reduction was noted, changes were not statistically significant. This could be due to several factors: biological variability, the short duration of follow-up, or the influence of high baseline adiposity on peptide clearance and production. Indeed, natriuretic peptide levels are known to be suppressed in obese individuals, which may limit their sensitivity as markers of therapeutic response in this population. The obesity paradox once again emerges as a potential explanatory framework, complicating straightforward interpretation of biomarker changes in the context of advanced metabolic disease (Guglin et al. 2014; Ha Manh et al. 2023).

Blood pressure reductions, particularly in systolic and diastolic values, were observed primarily in the GLP-1RA and dual therapy groups, supporting prior evidence that these agents have a favorable effect on vascular tone and autonomic regulation. Given the near-ubiquitous presence of hypertension in this population, such changes may be of considerable clinical importance. Indeed, hypertension remains a key driver of both left atrial and ventricular dysfunction, and its control is an essential element in the multifaceted management of HFpEF (Bykova et al. 2024).

These findings emphasize the necessity of a personalized, integrated therapeutic approach in managing complex cardiometabolic patients. The data suggest that GLP-1RA, particularly when combined with SGLT2i, can exert meaningful improvements in sleep-disordered breathing, metabolic parameters, and cardiovascular function—possibly through a synergistic mechanism grounded in weight loss, hemodynamic unloading, and neurohormonal modulation (Belli et al. 2022). While structural cardiac changes may require longer exposure or additional interventions, early functional and symptomatic gains may pave the way for downstream remodeling (Rolek et al. 2023). The consistency of BMI reduction across functional domains underlines weight loss as a therapeutic axis around which these improvements converge and reinforces its role as both a target and a mediator of benefit.

Survival outcomes observed at 6 months further contextualize these physiological improvements. Patients receiving dual therapy experienced the highest survival rate, with a mean survival time approaching 6 months and only a limited number of adverse events. Although survival analysis does not establish causality, this divergence in event-free survival between groups may reflect the cumulative effect of the observed improvements in sleep apnea severity, glycemic control, hemodynamics, and inflammation (Neuen et al. 2024). The GLP-1RA component, with its consistent association with BMI reduction and amelioration of both metabolic and cardiovascular markers, appears to be the key driver of these benefits. This survival signal, emerging over a relatively short timeframe, supports the hypothesis that functional improvements – particularly those rooted in weight reduction – may translate into tangible clinical benefits when appropriately targeted in multimorbid populations (Gourdy et al. 2023).

Limitations of the study

This study has several limitations that warrant consideration. First, the absence of patient randomization may introduce selection bias. Additional bias is possible due to the lack of a control group. However, from an ethical standpoint, random assignment to treatment or no-treatment arms in patients already indicated for GLP-1RA or SGLT2i therapy would not have been feasible. Instead, the study aimed to reflect real-world clinical practice and therapeutic decision-making, thereby enhancing external validity. Second, sleep-disordered breathing was assessed using a home-based ApneaLink device rather than a full polysomnogra-

phy study. While this may reduce diagnostic precision, the home-monitoring approach offers significant advantages in terms of accessibility, patient comfort, and cost-effectiveness. It also enabled the inclusion of a larger cohort, which would have been more challenging with resource-intensive in-lab diagnostics. Third, the statistical power of the study is influenced by group size. Although meaningful differences were observed across key parameters, certain comparisons may be underpowered, particularly for biomarker-based outcomes. Future studies with larger sample sizes are needed to confirm and expand upon these findings. Lastly, the duration of follow-up was relatively short. While six months is sufficient to detect functional and metabolic changes, it may not be long enough to capture structural cardiac remodeling or long-term clinical outcomes. Extended observation periods will be essential to establish the durability and prognostic implications of the observed improvements.

Conclusion

In this prospective study of patients with HFpEF, T2DM, obesity, and OSA, dual therapy with GLP-1RA and SGLT2i demonstrated significant improvements across cardiometabolic, respiratory, and functional domains. Weight loss appeared to be a key driver of these favorable changes, particularly regarding sleep parameters and echocardiographic function. While structural cardiac remodeling was not evident within the 6-month follow-up, early functional and biomarker shifts suggest a promising therapeutic impact. These findings highlight the potential of integrated pharmacological strategies in complex, multimorbid populations.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Sofia (Protocol No. 1316, approval date: December 13, 2021). All procedures were conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, and all participants provided written informed consent prior to enrollment.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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